

BIRINCHI TARTIBLI HOSILA YORDAMIDA FUNKSIYANING EKSTREMUMGA TEKSHIRISH, FUNKSIYANING EKSTREMUMLARI.

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ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqolada funksiyani o’sish va kamayish oraliqlariga tekshirish haqida ma’lumot keltirilgan va misollar ishlab ko’rsatilgan.

Ta’rif: Agar argumentning (a, b) oraliqqa tegishli katta qiymatiga funksiyaning katta qiymati mos kelsa, ya’ni $x_2 > x_1$ tengsizlikdan, bunda x_1, x_2 lar (a, b) intervalga tegishli, $f(x_2) > f(x_1)$ tengsizlik kelib chiqsa, u holda $y = f(x)$ funksiya shu (a, b) intervalda **o’suvchi funksiya** deyiladi.

Ta’rif: Agar biror (a, b) intervalda argumentning katta qiymatiga funksiyaning kichik qiymati mos kelsa, ya’ni agar $x_2 > x_1$ tengsizlikdan, bunda $x_1, x_2 \in (a, b), f(x_2) < f(x_1)$ tengsizlik kelib chiqsa, u holda $y = f(x)$ funksiya (a, b) intervalda **kamayuvchi funksiya** deyiladi.

Teorema.(funksiya o’suvchi bo’lishining zaruriy sharti) Agar (a, b) intervalda differensiallanuvchi $y = f(x)$ funksiya o’suvchi bo’lsa, u holda bu funksiyaning hosilasi intervalning hamma nuqtasida manfiy bo’lmasligi zarur, ya’ni barcha $x \in (a, b)$ uchun $f'(x) \geq 0$

Teorema.(funksiya o’suvchi bo’lishining yetarlilik sharti) Agar $[a, b]$ kesmada uzluksiz bo’lgan $y = f(x)$ funksiya har bir ichki nuqtada musbat hosilaga ega bo’lsa, u holda bu funksiya $[a, b]$ kesmada **o’suvchi** bo’ladi.

Teorema.(funksiya kamayuvchi bo’lishining yetarlilik sharti) Agar $[a, b]$ kesmada uzluksiz $y = f(x)$ funksiya bu kesmaning har bir ichki nuqtasida manfiy hosilaga ega bo’lsa, u holda bu funksiya $[a, b]$ kesmada kamayuvchi bo’ladi.

1-misol. $y = 3x^6$ funksiyaning monotonlik intervallarini toping.

Yechish. Y’ hosilani topamiz: $y' = 18x^5$

$x < 0$ da $y' < 0$ funksiya kamayadi.

$x > 0$ da funksiya o'sadi.

Aytaylik $f(x)$ funksiya (a, b) intervalda aniqlangan va $x_0 \in (a, b)$ bo'lsin.

Ta'rif. Agar x_0 nuqtaning shunday $(x_0 - \epsilon; x_0 + \epsilon)$ atrofi mavjud bo'lib, shu atrofdan olingan ixtiyoriy x uchun $f(x) \geq f(x_0)$ ($f(x) \leq f(x_0)$) tenglik o'rinli bo'lsa, u holda x_0 nuqta $f(x)$ funksiyaning maksimum (minimum) nuqtasi, $f(x_0)$ esa funksiyaning maksimumi (minimumi) deb ataladi.

Ta'rif. Agar x_0 nuqtaning shunday 1-
chizma

atrofi $(x_0 - \epsilon; x_0 + \epsilon)$ mavjud bo'lib, shu atrofdan olingan ixtiyoriy $x \in (x_0 - \epsilon; x_0 + \epsilon)$ uchun $f(x) < f(x_0)$ ($f(x) > f(x_0)$) tengsizlik o'rinli bo'lsa, u holda $f(x)$ funksiya x_0 nuqtada qat'iy maksimumga (minimumga) ega deyiladi.

Funksiyaning maksimum va minimum nuqtalari funksiyaning **ekstremum** nuqtalari, maksimum va minimum qiymatlari funksiyaning **ekstremumlari** deb ataladi.

Shuningdek, $f(x)$ funksiya (a, b) intervalda bir qancha maksimum va minimumlarga ega bo'lishi, maksimum qiymati uning ba'zi bir minimum qiymatidan kichik bo'lishi ham mumkin. Masalan grafi 1-chizmada ko'rsatilgan $y=f(x)$ funksiya uchun $x=a$ nuqtada lokal maksimum, $x=b$ nuqtada lokal minimum mavjud bo'lib, $f(a) < f(b)$ tengsizlik o'rinli.

Eslatma 1. Agar funksiya $[a, b]$ kesmada aniqlangan bo'lsa, bu funksiya o'zining maksimum va minimumlariga x ning shu kesma ichidagi qiymatlaridagina erishadi.

Eslatma 2. Funksiyaning $[a, b]$ kesmadagi maksimum va minimumlari har doim ham uning shu kesmadagi eng katta yoki eng kichik qiymati bo'lavermaydi: maksimum nuqtasida funksiya eng katta qiymatni maksimum nuqtasiga yetarlicha yaqin nuqtalardagi qiymatlariga nisbatangina qabul qiladi. Maksimum minimumdan kichik bo'lib qolishi mumkin

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